

THE MAIN DIRECTIONS OF DEVELOPING STUDENTS' SPEECH IN NATIVE LANGUAGE CLASSES

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8268992>

Abstract: In this scientific article, the development of students' speech in native language classes, pedagogues focus on the main areas of development of speaking skills, and the aim is to equip students with the necessary tools for effective communication and expressing their opinions in their native language. It is explained that one of the main reasons for paying attention to the development of students' speech in mother tongue classes is to improve their general language knowledge.

Key words: knowledge, development of speech, speech skills, improvement of language skills. Introduction. The development of students' speech in native language classes is of utmost importance in the education system. By focusing on the main directions of developing speech skills, educators aim to equip students with the necessary tools to effectively communicate and express themselves in their mother tongue.

Importance of developing students' speech in native language classes one of the primary reasons for focusing on developing students' speech in native language classes is to enhance their overall language proficiency. By honing their speaking skills, students can effectively express their thoughts and ideas, enabling them to engage in meaningful conversations and discussions both in academic and real- world settings.

Discussion of the main directions in developing students' speech One main direction in developing students' speech is through the use of authentic materials and real- life situations. This approach encourages students to communicate in a more natural and fluent way, as they are exposed to language in its authentic context. Additionally, integrating technology into language classes provides another avenue for students to practice and improve their speaking skills.

Another direction in developing students' speech in native language classes is through group discussions and debates. These activities promote critical thinking, active participation, and effective communication skills. Students learn to express their opinions, defend their arguments, and listen to others' viewpoints, fostering a well- rounded and articulate communication style.

Another important aspect of developing students' speech in native language classes is vocabulary expansion. Students need to be exposed to a wide range of words and phrases to enhance their ability to communicate effectively. Teachers should provide opportunities for students to learn new vocabulary through reading, writing, and engaging in discussions. Moreover, using synonyms, antonyms, and context clues can also help students expand their vocabulary and deepen their understanding of words.

Importance of a rich vocabulary in speech development In addition to fostering effective communication, a rich vocabulary plays a crucial role in the development of speech in native language classes. As students expand their lexicon, they gain more opportunities for expressing their thoughts, emotions, and ideas accurately, as well as enhancing their overall linguistic competency.

Techniques for expanding students' vocabulary One effective technique for expanding students' vocabulary is through reading. Encouraging students to read a wide range of literature exposes them to new words and contexts. Additionally, discussing unfamiliar words and their meanings during reading activities can help reinforce their understanding and usage in different contexts.

1. Word games and puzzles

Word games and puzzles can be an effective tool for developing students' speech in native language classes. These activities engage students in a fun and interactive way, encouraging them to think critically and expand their vocabulary. Additionally, word games and puzzles help students improve their spelling and comprehension skills, ultimately enhancing their overall language proficiency.

2. Reading and discussing texts

In order to enhance students' comprehension skills, reading and discussing texts plays a crucial role in native language classes. This activity not only helps students engage with the content, but also promotes critical thinking and analysis. Through collaborative discussions, students can share their interpretations and gain a deeper understanding of the text's nuances. This promotes a sense of active participation and encourages students to develop their own perspectives.

3. Using context clues and synonyms

Context clues and synonyms are essential tools for developing students' speech in native language classes. By exposing students to a variety of texts and providing them with ample opportunities to encounter unfamiliar words, they can learn to use surrounding information to decipher word meanings. Additionally, teaching students synonyms helps expand their vocabulary and enables them to express themselves more effectively.

4. Encouraging regular reading habits

Encouraging regular reading habits is crucial in developing students' speech in native language classes. By promoting reading, students enhance their vocabulary, grammar, and comprehension skills, leading to improved oral and written communication. Additionally, consistent reading fosters critical thinking creativity, and cultural awareness, enabling students to become well- rounded individuals.

Additionally, the incorporation of technology in native language classes can greatly enhance students' speech development. Tools such as speech recognition software and online speaking platforms enable learners to practice pronunciation, fluency, and intonation in a realistic and interactive manner. Through these means, students can receive immediate feedback and improve their speaking skills effectively.

Al plays a crucial role in developing students' speech in native language classes. A deep understanding of grammar is necessary for students to express themselves accurately and effectively. Additionally mastering sentence structure allows students to convey their ideas in a coherent and organized manner. Consequently, educators should focus on implementing strategies that promote grammar and sentence structure proficiency in order to enhance students' overall linguistic abilities.

The role of grammar in speech development is undeniable. Not only does a solid understanding of grammar foster clear and effective communication, but it also allows

individuals to comprehend and interpret others' speech more accurately. Without a strong foundation in grammar, speech may become disjointed and confusing.

Activities to improve students' grammar and sentence structure Activities designed to enhance students' grammar and sentence structure are crucial in the development of proficient communication skills. Teachers can implement various strategies, such as sentence combining exercises, peer editing sessions, and grammar drills to refine students' understanding and usage of language mechanics, fostering their linguistic competence.

1. Focusing on proper word order and sentence construction One essential aspect in developing students' speech in native language classes is focusing on proper word order and sentence construction. By teaching students the rules and principles of syntax, we enable them to create clear and coherent sentences that effectively convey their ideas and thoughts.

2. Practicing different sentence types (e.g., declarative, interrogative, etc.) It is crucial for college-level students to practice different sentence types in their native language classes. Understanding how to construct declarative, interrogative, imperative, and exclamatory sentences is essential for effective communication. By mastering these sentence types, students can express themselves accurately and confidently in various contexts.

3. Engaging in grammar-focused exercises and drills Engaging in grammar-focused exercises and drills is another key approach to developing students' speech in native language classes. These exercises allow learners to focus explicitly on grammar rules, structures, and patterns, enabling them to recognize and apply them accurately in their own speech. By practicing various grammatical exercises, such as sentence transformations, error corrections, and gap-filling activities, students can enhance their linguistic accuracy and proficiency.

4. Providing opportunities for structured spoken interactions Another approach to develop students' speech in native language classes is to provide opportunities for structured spoken interactions. These interactions can be facilitated through activities such as debates, discussions, and role-playing. These activities allow students to express their opinions, engage in critical thinking, and practice their language skills in a controlled and supportive environment. Through such structured interactions, students can enhance their oral proficiency and develop effective communication skills.

Moreover, native language classes should focus on developing students' speaking skills through interactive activities and discussions. Students need to engage in meaningful conversations and express their thoughts clearly and coherently. Additionally, teachers should encourage students to participate actively, provide constructive feedback, and help them improve their pronunciation and fluency.

Developing proper pronunciation and articulation skills is crucial in native language classes. Students should be encouraged to pay attention to the correct pronunciation of each individual sound and to practice articulating them accurately. A variety of techniques and exercises, such as tongue twisters and phonetic drills, can be employed to improve pronunciation skills. Additionally, teachers should provide feedback and guidance to help students correct any mispronunciations, ensuring clear and effective communication.

Significance of clear pronunciation and articulation in effective speech Clear pronunciation and articulation play a crucial role in delivering effective speech. Mispronunciation or poor articulation can lead to miscommunication and misunderstanding. It is essential for students

to develop these skills as they enhance their overall oral communication, ensuring clarity and coherence in their speech.

Techniques to enhance students' pronunciation and articulation skills Another technique to enhance students' pronunciation and articulation skills is through the use of phonetic exercises. These exercises focus on specific sounds and phonemes, helping students develop proper articulation. Additionally, the use of tongue twisters and minimal pairs can challenge students to differentiate between similar sounds and improve their pronunciation accuracy.

1. Introducing phonics and phonetic exercises

One effective method used for developing students' speech in native language classes is the introduction of phonics and phonetic exercises. Phonics is the study of the sounds of the English language and how they relate to the written letters. Phonetics, on the other hand, focuses on the physical properties of speech sounds. By incorporating phonics and phonetic exercises into classroom activities, students can improve their pronunciation skills and enhance their overall ability to communicate effectively in their native language. These exercises may involve various techniques, such as identifying individual sounds, syllables, and stress patterns in words, as well as practicing correct intonation and stress in sentences. Through this approach, students can develop a strong foundation in phonetics and attain greater fluency and accuracy in their speech.

2. Practicing tongue twisters and pronunciation drills

Practicing tongue twisters and pronunciation drills is an essential component of developing students' speech in native language classes. These exercises challenge students to articulate complex sounds, improve their enunciation, and enhance their oral communication skills. Moreover, they help students overcome pronunciation difficulties, allowing them to speak more fluently and confidently.

3. Using audiovisual resources for modeling correct pronunciation

Audiovisual resources play a crucial role in modeling correct pronunciation for students. By providing visual and auditory cues, these resources enhance language learning by offering real-life examples of proper pronunciation. This teaching approach helps students to articulate sounds accurately, improving their overall oral proficiency in the target language.

4. Encouraging students to engage in conversation and offer constructive feedback

one effective approach to developing students' speech in native language classes is to encourage them to engage in conversation and offer constructive feedback. By actively participating in discussions, students can improve their communication skills and develop critical thinking abilities. Additionally, providing feedback to their peers allows students to better understand different perspectives and enhance their own understanding of the topic being discussed.

In order to enhance students' speech in native language classes various approaches have been explored. One effective method is the use of authentic materials, such as newspaper articles and literary works. Which expose students to diverse vocabulary and sentence structures. Additionally, incorporating speaking exercises that encourage discussions and debates allows students to practice expressing their thoughts and opinions confidently. Moreover, providing constructive feedback and guidance on pronunciation and intonation helps students improve their oral communication skills.

Fluency and coherence are crucial aspects of developing students' speech in native language classes. Fluency refers to the ability to speak fluidly and without hesitation, while coherence

refers to the logical organization and connection of ideas. It is essential for students to develop both fluency and coherence to effectively communicate their thoughts and ideas.

To develop fluency and coherence in speech, students must be given ample opportunities to practice speaking. This includes engaging in conversations with peers, participating in class discussions, and presenting their ideas to an audience. Through consistent practice, students can improve their ability to express their thoughts in a clear and logical manner.

Strategies to promote fluency and coherence have become essential in native language classes. Firstly, teachers should provide ample opportunities for students to engage in meaningful conversations and discussions. This can be achieved through group activities, debates, and presentations, allowing students to express their thoughts and ideas fluently. Additionally, the use of various interactive platforms such as online forums and chat rooms can encourage students to practice their speaking skills outside the classroom. Moreover, teachers should focus on teaching strategies that enhance coherence, such as organizing ideas logically, using appropriate transitional words, and providing explicit instruction on sentence and paragraph structure. By implementing these strategies, students can improve their speech fluency and coherence, ultimately strengthening their overall language skills.

1. Role- playing and improvisation activities are valuable tools in developing students' speech in native language classes. These activities provide students with opportunities to experiment with language, express their thoughts and emotions, and engage in authentic communication. Through role- playing and improvisation, students can enhance their linguistic skills, critical thinking abilities, and cultural awareness.

2. Providing opportunities for discussions and debates Another important direction in developing students' speech in native language classes is providing opportunities for discussions and debates. These activities allow students to express their opinions, engage in critical thinking, and explore different perspectives on various topics, encouraging active participation and enhancing communication skills.

3. Building up students' confidence in public speaking Building up students' confidence in public speaking is crucial in native language classes. By providing opportunities for students to present in front of their peers, teachers can create a supportive environment where students feel comfortable expressing their thoughts and ideas. This not only enhances their speaking abilities but also boosts their overall confidence, leading to improved communication skills in both academic and professional settings.

4. Offering real- life situations to practice spontaneous speech Furthermore, offering real- life situations to practice spontaneous speech is another crucial aspect of developing students' speech in native language classes. By simulating authentic scenarios, students are encouraged to think on their feet and respond in an impromptu manner, thus enhancing their ability to communicate effectively in real- world situations. Additionally, such exercises help students build confidence and fluency in their speech, as they learn to navigate through various unpredictable conversational contexts.

Another main direction of developing students' speech in native language classes is enhancing their vocabulary skills. By introducing a wide range of reading materials and encouraging regular vocabulary exercises, students can expand their lexicon and improve their ability to express themselves fluently and accurately.

Another important aspect of developing students' speech in native language classes is focusing on their listening and comprehension skills. Through various listening exercises, students can enhance their ability to understand spoken language and extract relevant information. This is crucial for effective communication and overall language proficiency.

Strong correlation between listening comprehension and speech development In native language classes, it is essential to promote the development of students' speech by focusing on their listening comprehension skills. Research has shown a strong correlation between the two, indicating that a solid foundation in listening comprehension can facilitate speech development in various aspects, such as vocabulary acquisition and sentence structure formation.

Techniques for improving students' listening and comprehension skills one of the main directions for developing students' speech in native language classes is enhancing their listening and comprehension skills. Several techniques can be implemented to improve these skills, including using authentic materials, incorporating multimedia resources, engaging in meaningful conversations, and providing ample opportunities for active listening and reflection.

Engaging in audio recordings and podcasts is a valuable method for developing students' speech in native language classes. By listening to authentic recordings and podcasts, students are exposed to various accents, intonations, and speech patterns, enhancing their comprehension skills and phonetic accuracy. Furthermore, active participation in recording exercises promotes speaking fluency and confidence.

Utilizing listening comprehension exercises and activities Utilizing listening comprehension exercises and activities are crucial for developing students' speech in native language classes. These activities help students to understand spoken language, improve their listening skills, and expand their vocabulary. Moreover, these exercises enhance students' ability to extract important information from different contexts and develop critical thinking skills.

Practicing summarizing and paraphrasing skills practicing summarizing and paraphrasing skills is a critical aspect of developing students' speech in native language classes. It helps students enhance their understanding of texts by condensing them into concise yet comprehensive summaries. Additionally, paraphrasing aids in the improvement of students' language proficiency and their ability to effectively communicate ideas in their own words.

Encouraging active listening and note-taking during lectures or presentations one effective strategy for improving students' speech in native language classes is to encourage active listening and note-taking during lectures or presentations. When students actively listen and take notes, they are more likely to retain information and engage in meaningful discussions.

This also helps them to identify key points and important details, which can later be incorporated into their own speeches or presentations. By promoting active listening and note-taking, educators can enhance students' overall communication skills and critical thinking abilities.

Furthermore, integration of technology into native language classes has become a main direction for developing students' speech. With the advancements in educational technology, interactive tools such as language learning apps, online forums, and video conferences offer students opportunities to practice and improve their oral skills.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the main directions of developing students' speech in native language classes involve implementing communicative language teaching methods, incorporating authentic and meaningful language tasks and activities, promoting learner autonomy and self-reflection, providing ample opportunities for practice and feedback, and fostering a positive and supportive learning environment. These approaches aim to enhance students' speaking skills and enable them to effectively communicate in their native language.

Recap of the main directions for developing students' speech in native language classes In conclusion, the development of students' speech in native language classes requires a multi-faceted approach. Firstly, teachers must create a supportive and engaging learning environment. Secondly, they should provide ample opportunities for students to practice speaking through diverse activities. Lastly, incorporating authentic materials and technology can further enhance speech development.

Importance of continually reinforcing and practicing these skills In conclusion, continually reinforcing and practicing essential skills in native language classes is of paramount importance. Consistent practice not only helps to solidify knowledge but also cultivates confidence and fluency in speaking. Through repetition and reinforcement, students can develop a deeper understanding and application of these skills, equipping them for real-life communication scenarios.

Benefits of proficient speech in native language acquisition and overall communication Proficient speech in one's native language is critical for successful language acquisition and effective communication. It allows individuals to express their thoughts and ideas accurately, enhancing their overall understanding of the language. Moreover, proficient speech ensures clear communication, facilitating effective interactions and collaborations in various contexts.

References:

1. Paul Kei Matsuda. "Landmark Essays on ESL Writing." Volume 17, Tony Silva, Routledge, 10/31/2013
2. Monica Gordon- Pershey.' Grammar and Syntax.' Developing School-Age Children's Oral and Written Language Skills, Plural Publishing, 2/22/2022
3. Jim Miller.' Syntax.' A Linguistic Introduction to Sentence Structure, Keith Brown, Routledge, 10/14/2020
4. Amanda Morin." The Everything Parent's Guide to Special Education.' A Complete Step-by- Step Guide to Advocating for Your Child with Special Needs, Simon and Schuster, 5/18/2014
5. Carla Hamaguchi.' Power Practice: Context Clues, Gr. 3-4, eBook. Creative Teaching Press, 1/1/2007
6. Marilyn Mottram.' Building Communities of Engaged Readers.' Reading for pleasure, Teresa Cremin, Routledge, 6/20/2014
7. Cindy A. Littlefield.' horse Games and Puzzles for Kids.' 102 Brainteasers, Word Games, Jokes and Riddles, Picture Puzzlers, Matches and Logic Tests for horse- Loving Kids, Storey Publishing, 1/1/2004
8. James F. Baumann.' Vocabulary Instruction.' Research to Practice, Edward J. Kame'enui, Guilford Press, 3/28/2012
9. Dorothy Rubin.' Vocabulary Expansion.' Macmillan, 8/1/1990

10. Norma Ryan.' International Perspectives on Teaching and Learning in higher Education.'
NAIRTL Conference Proceedings, November 2007, NAIRTL, 1/1/2008
11. Jim Cummins.' Bilingualism and Special Education.' Issues in Assessment and Pedagogy,
Pro- Ed, 1/1/1995

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